

TOWARDS A FLOW-ACCURATE LUNAR REGOLITH SIMULANT. Olfa D'Angelo^{1,2}, Léonie Gasteiner² and Naomi Murdoch², ¹ Van der Waals-Zeeman Institute, Institute of Physics, University of Amsterdam, Science Park 904, Amsterdam 1098XH, The Netherlands (o.dangelo@uva.nl), ² Institut Supérieur de l'Aéronautique et de l'Espace (ISAE-SUPAERO), Université de Toulouse, 10 Avenue Marc Pégélin, 31055 Toulouse, France.

Introduction: Lunar regolith is a deceptively complex material: it has repeatedly challenged surface operations during Moon missions. While chemical and physical simulants exist to mimic regolith for pre-mission testing, their mechanical fidelity remains critically lacking. The discrepancy between laboratory-tested performance and actual lunar behavior has led to mission setbacks.

Rheological Regolith Simulant: We address this challenge by developing lunar regolith simulants that accurately reproduces the mechanical and rheological behavior of true lunar regolith, as observed *in-situ* on the Moon. We explore experimental strategies to tailor the flow behavior of existing simulants, with a focus on modifying interparticle cohesion. Through rheological and granular mechanics tests – including penetration resistance, direct shear, and angle of repose – we quantify how these modifications impact simulant behavior.

An Open Database of Lunar Regolith and Simulants Properties: A crucial step in this effort is benchmarking against actual lunar soil properties. To do so, we created a publicly accessible, curated database summarizing all existing measurements of lunar regolith mechanical and rheological behavior, drawn from Apollo, Luna, and robotic mission archives. This open resource will serve both as a validation backbone for simulant development and as a reference tool for the broader communities working on granular materials in space. Ultimately, we aim not only to engineer better analog materials, but to set a new standard for transparent, reproducible testing of granular systems in extraterrestrial environments.

References: [1] L. Gasteiner, N. Murdoch, O. D'Angelo (2026) [preprint] *ArXiv:2602.03829*.